

Thiazole Compounds

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In continuation of the previous work on thiazole compounds¹, we now report the preparations of a few compounds containing two thiazole nuclei with two *p*-bromophenyl or two thienyl nuclei.

Condensation of two moles of *p*-bromophenacyl bromide with one mole of rubenic acid proceeded smoothly giving rise to 4,4'-(*di-p-bromophenyl*)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (I). When two moles of 2-bromoacetylthiophen² were allowed to react with one mole of rubenic acid, the product was 4,4'-(*di-α-thienyl*)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (II). Dithiazolyls generally show intense fluorescence and are halochromic; but these two compounds do not show any fluorescence, either in daylight or in UV light.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) 4,4'-(*Di-p-bromophenyl*)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (I).—A solution of 5.6 g. (0.02 mole) *p*-bromophenacyl bromide in 50 ml alcohol was mixed with a solution of 1.2 g. (0.01 mole) rubenic acid in 40 ml alcohol. The mixture was kept under continuous reflux for 5 hr. After 30 minutes of reflux, the condensation product started to separate. It was cooled, filtered, and washed with cold alcohol and ether, then dried. Grey flakes with metallic glaze were obtained. Recrystallization from pyridine gave shining snow white crystals, m.p. 224–225°, (yield: 3.5 g., 73%). This compound was slightly soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and dioxane. (Found: C, 45.37; H, 1.96; N, 5.60; S, 13.47. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₀N₂S₂Br₂: C, 45.20; H, 2.10; N, 5.85; S, 13.40).

(b) 4,4'-(*Di-α-thienyl*)-2,2'-dithiazolyl (II).—The same procedure was followed as in (a). The condensation of 4.1 g. (0.02 mole) 2-bromoacetylthiophene and 1.2 g. (0.01 mole) rubenic acid gave the crude condensation product from which on recrystallization from

1. J. Shukri, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 651.

2. *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2891.

pyridine, a product of pale yellow shining crystals were obtained, m.p. 277-278°. (yield: 2 g. 60%). This compound was soluble in acetone, benzene, chloroform, dioxane and H_2SO_4 ; slightly soluble in alcohol. (Found: C, 50.61; H, 2.37; N, 8.52; S, 38.42. Calc. for $C_{14}H_8N_2S_4$: C, 50.57; H, 2.42; N, 8.42; S, 38.57).

All m.p.s. are uncorrected, and were measured on Kofler block. Microanalysis was carried out by Alfred Berhardt Max-Planck Institute, Ruhr, Germany.

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